

Publishers, Organization providing identifiers, and Libraries

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Abstract:

Scripts, in general; publications, are one of essential sources of education, and without being like as a Marketeer, or a Saleman, discussing about products, we shall attempt to discuss, about generality in publication industry, though author lacks knowledge, if such record keeping are done or not, based on numerical identification for each work, among any two bodies, or three bodies, because generally, it is library that does cataloguing of books and any datas.

Keywords: Metadata, Keywords, Abstracts, Identifiers, Publishers, Cataloguing of Data

Introduction:

Fellows who have published, their manuscripts or works, might have been familier with reference number, Inquiry number, submission number, thus we shall begin with same numbers to discuss our discussion. For an example, any publisher, did published my manuscript or work, with some 123, or 1, as their work, then, that would mean, my work is registered on their administration, for work procedure.

That would mean,any publisher, and all publishers, does have their own unique numerical identification, for any manuscript submitted to them. Let us take an example with my own firm, Mental Asylum of Education, and for my firm, when I would receive any submission, then, as per my record keeping, that would be Manuscript No:1, of Mental Asylum of Education.

That is same for all publishers, and they do have their own numbers, which too, are unique, and must have to be unique, for proper record keeping, and archival.

Aftermath:

After my firm would look, review manuscript, then decision are made, either to reject, or to publish. Then that would again begun, numerical identification for Mental Asylum of Education.

If Accepted, then Manuscript Number 1, got accepted, and would proceed towards publications, which too would have numerical identification, of Manuscript published No:1.

If we would talk about case of rejection, then Manuscript No 1 got rejected would be seen, where as, as per gradual submission, based on Manuscript number of receipts and registration, some new manuscript; suppose Manuscript number 2 got accepted, and got published as Manuscript as Number 1.

In those two cases, we have discussed for acceptance and rejection of manuscripts, and Manuscript Number 1, published are different in each caaes.

For Internal Purpose of my Administration:

Since we have manuscript accepted, as well as manuscript rejected, Manuscript registration number would be for my own internal purpose. Like as Manuscript Number 1, got published as Manuscript number 1 Published, making two branches of Published, and Not-Published, based on initial registration number of manuscript.

In General, in tabular (without table) form, it would look like as following:

Manuscript Receipt Number	Decision	Manuscript Published Number
1.	Accepted.	1
2.	Rejected.	
3.	Accepted.	2

That would be an general example, for each and every publication house, as per their record keeping.

Further Identifiers:

ISBN number, ISSN number, DOI number, are further identifiers, needed for my firm, as well as any publishers, where as Manuscript Published Number 1, would be unique identifier of my firm Mental Asylum of Education.

Question: Where did we missed Open Accessing?

Most of us, do establish business firms, or even institutions, or even Universities, by talking as Not-For Profit, and do talk, entirely devoted for the welfare of peoples, and service oriented. Our Question

begins, about production cost, as well as identifiers. To get a ISBN number too, we have to submit our manuscript, to get a DOI number, too we need to submit manuscript, and I don't know, if ISSN number, does seeks published volumes of each issues or not, like as of ISBN, and DOI.

Answer is simple, It is due to Market, Business, Competition, and, most of all, Privacy Policies, are the topics, that doesn't allows open accessing of documents.

Libraries:

Libraries too are same like as publishers, doing catalogig of books, but they keep books, of all publishers, whereas catalog of Publishers, contains materials, only published by them.

Problem in Metadata:

With recent advances in citation techniques referencing styles, metadata still does put question. Suppose, while submitting manuscript data, or book data, like as abstract, blurb, description, keywords, comments, book covers, we provide data for brief introduction to our book. While doing import and export of citations, if we are able to do by computed means, then that would be accurate and same, where as if would do manually, and if our data aren't consistent, then, that becomes problem, while doing abstraction, indexing, as well as cataloging. For an example, I had submitted book data to JustFiction Edition, an imprint of Omniscryptum Publication, and got rejected Then I submitted to Zenodo, and got published. I even did created a registry list(or listed), in ORCID, and in all those three different organizations, my metadata might not be consistent, which then creates problems.

For Publishers:

Since each publisher has their own unique identification number, by means of membership, co-operation, or by means of submitting documents to get other identifiers like as ISBN, ISSN, DOI, ORCID, Pubmed, and variety of identifiers can be found, among which, many might be publisher's own identification number provided to users, relying on user registration. My user profile in Orcid, and all publishers where I have made accounts, are same.

That would mean, the table would be like as

User Number(Identification) Manuscript Number Decision. Manuscript Published Number

Conclusion:

Besides our own unique identification; quality, quantity, number of readers, does plays role, along with legacy in publication with quality, to discuss about impacts and quality as a tool of marketing and advertisement, without any cost.

Actknowledgements:

To all rejected fellows